

STUDIES OF COMPETITIVE MARKET MECHANISMS IN THE ELECTRIC POWER INDUSTRY WHILE ENSURING THE INTEGRATION OF RENEWABLE ENERGY SOURCES

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Abstract. *The paper highlights reforms in Uzbekistan, including unbundling of ownership, increased private sector participation in electricity generation, and the development of renewable energy. Despite notable progress, the lack of a fully competitive electricity market and continued reliance on long-term power purchase agreements (PPAs) present structural problems that may hinder long-term flexibility and integration of renewable energy. Based on a study of international experience, a scheme for renewable energy support by the government of Uzbekistan is presented. Based on the introduction of renewable energy technology into the energy sector, separate companies responsible for generation, transmission and distribution of electricity will be established. At the same time, the functions of purchase and sale of electricity will be divided according to the newly developed scheme of the electricity sector of Uzbekistan. Research and development work is underway to develop a recommendation for Uzbekistan to create a sustainable, market-oriented energy system, as well as recommendations for future studies on the integration of variable renewable energy sources (VRES) into competitive wholesale and retail markets.*

Keywords: *energy sector reforms, competitive electricity markets, wholesale market, retail market, market mechanisms, variable renewable energy, market liberalization, Uzbekistan energy reforms.*

The electricity sector plays a vital role in both economic growth of a country and individuals' everyday lives, accounting over 20% of global final energy consumption. While it is projected that demand will rise by 60% by 2040, driven by electrification and digitalization, efficient and reliable supply increasingly essential. Implementing competitive market frameworks in the energy sector can assist to reduce costs by up to 20%, enhance transparency, and attract private investments for sustainable energy transitions [1]. In Uzbekistan, electricity demand is expected to grow significantly due to economic development and increased electrification. It is projected that Uzbekistan will experience a sharp rise in electricity demand, driven by economic growth and expanded electrification. To meet this growing need sustainably and reliably, introducing market mechanisms in the sector is crucial to ensure efficiency, transparency, and private sector participation.

Between 2012 and 2019 Uzbekistan's the electricity generation grew at an average annual rate of 2.6 percent annually, which was not enough to meet the rising demand. During this period, the electricity supply gap stood at around 9.4%. [2]. In 2019, Uzbekistan had a total installed power capacity of 15 GW, producing approximately 63.5 GWh of electricity annually – nearly 96% of which was generated from fossil fuels, primarily natural gas and coal. Despite this level of

generation, demand stood at 52.68 GWh, and high transmission and distribution losses further exacerbated the sector's inefficiencies. At the time, the electricity sector of Uzbekistan functioned under a vertically integrated, wholly state-owned enterprise, with a single entity managing generation, transmission, and distribution activities. The sector experienced lack of renewable energy sources in the energy mix and private sector involvement, with no financial or policy incentives in place to promote investment or innovation. Electricity tariffs remained low, discouraging efficiency improvements and limiting the attractiveness of the sector for potential investors [3].

By the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the period from 2019 to 2024 saw significant reforms as the government prioritized energy security, efficiency, and sustainability. A key catalyst for reform was the country's rapid economic growth and industrialization, which significantly increased electricity demand. In response to the constraints of the existing system, the government implemented foreign direct investment policies aimed at attracting both domestic and international private investors to the energy sector. These policies provided incentives such as tax benefits, preferential tariffs for renewable energy, and others [4].

Fig.1. Renewable energy support from the Government of Uzbekistan

A significant milestone in the sector's transformation was the unbundling of the vertically integrated state-owned company which led to the establishment of distinct entities responsible for generation, transmission, and distribution. Later on, purchase and sale functions are also separated (Fig.2.).

Fig.2. Scheme of the power sector of Uzbekistan

Although this restructuring established a more defined regulatory framework, it did not lead to the development of a fully competitive electricity market. Private sector participation remained limited to independent power producers operating under long-term bilateral contracts through government-backed PPAs. Additionally, modernization initiatives were undertaken to upgrade the aging infrastructure, minimize energy losses, and enhance the overall reliability of the power supply.

Uzbekistan's energy market liberalization, initiated in 2019 and accelerating since 2024, shares many similarities with the early reforms of Türkiye and Georgia (and many other countries) – which transitioned from a vertically integrated, state-dominated system to a competitive, investor-friendly market. Experiences of these countries underlined several crucial success factors for effective liberalization, including the establishment of a strong legal and regulatory framework, independent regulation, unbundling of state utilities, and introduction incentives to attract more private investment.

However, analyzed international examples also underscore some common challenges that Uzbekistan may face in its reform process. These challenges might include market price volatility, social sensitivity and resistance to tariff reforms, and the slow development of wholesale markets. Addressing these obstacles will require carefully calibrated for Uzbekistan's realities policy measures, including but not limited to phased tariff adjustments, mechanisms for protecting vulnerable consumers, and gradual integration of renewable energy sources.

Based on the introduction of renewable energy technology into the energy sector, separate companies responsible for generation, transmission and distribution of electricity will be established. At the same time, the functions of purchase and sale of electricity will be divided according to the newly developed scheme of the electricity sector of Uzbekistan.

Research and development work is underway to develop a recommendation for Uzbekistan to create a sustainable, market-oriented energy system, as well as recommendations for future studies on the integration of variable renewable energy sources (VRES) into competitive wholesale and retail markets.

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